

Acidity and porosity properties of zeolites affect their catalytic performance in thymol synthesis

Fateme Poorsharbat Ghavi, Petr Golis, Martin Kubů, Jan Přeč, Maksym Opanasenko*

Department of Physical and Macromolecular Chemistry, Faculty of Sciences, Charles University, Hlavova 8, 128 43, Prague 2, Czech Republic

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ABSTRACT

Thymol is synthesized from m-cresol alkylation reaction with 2-propanol. A few commercial zeolites have been tested in this reaction, but the influence of acidity and porosity of a zeolite on the m-cresol conversion and thymol yield is scarcely studied. Isomorphously-substituted Al-, Ga-, Fe-, B-, and In-UTL with different hetero-elements and thus different ratio between strong and weak sites give insight into the effect of acidity. Isorecticular zeolites Al-UTL, Al-IPC-7, and Al-IPC-2 with different pore sizes reveal the effect of porosity. In this study, m-cresol conversion was far from comparable over Al-UTL or Ga-UTL (X = 18–19 %) and Fe-UTL, B-UTL, or In-UTL (X = 2–3 %) having different concentration of strong Brønsted acid sites. Thymol yield was also higher over Al- and Ga-UTL (Y = 11–13 %) than over Fe-, B-, and In-UTL (Y = 1–2 %). The easier accessibility to the strong Brønsted acid sites in Al-UTL, provided by bigger pore sizes, resulted in higher m-cresol conversion and thymol yield compared to Al-IPC-7 (X = 15 % and Y = 8 %) and Al-IPC-2 (X = 6 % and Y = 2 %). In addition, the stronger Brønsted acidity and large and extra-large porosity in Al-UTL and Ga-UTL facilitated the rearrangement of isopropyl-3-methylphenyl ether - the product of the O-alkylation pathway - to thymol. Thus, Al-UTL and Ga-UTL (along with Al-FAU reference material) confirmed the optimum structural properties for a high selectivity to thymol.

1. Introduction

2-Isopropyl-5-methylphenol, also known as thymol, is a natural volatile monoterpene. Thymol is present in essential oils of plant species, such as *Thymus vulgaris*, and it can be extracted from these oils by different solvents. Because of its insecticidal, antioxidant, antimicrobial, antifungal, and anti-inflammatory properties, thymol has found applications in agrochemical industry, food packaging, and medical products. Moreover, thymol can be hydrogenated to produce menthol, another important terpene and the major component of the essential oils with peppermint odor. The accessibility to natural thymol recovered from plant sources is time- and region-dependent, making it a valuable target product from synthetic routes [1–3].

Friedel-Crafts (FC) alkylation reaction of m-cresol with isopropyl alcohol leads to thymol through new C–C bond formation on the aromatic ring. This FC alkylation reaction can be catalyzed by homogenous acid catalysts (such as BF_3) or heterogeneous acid catalysts (such as Al_2O_3). Since homogeneous catalysts are not as thermally stable and environmentally friendly as the heterogeneous ones, thymol is

synthesized in industry via the liquid phase alkylation of m-cresol with 2-propanol over solid acid catalysts [4,5]. Among the industrially-used solid acids, zeolites play a prominent role and they are also applicable for this reaction.

Zeolites are crystalline microporous elementosilicates, composed of primary building units of TO_4 tetrahedra (T is commonly Si or Al) connected by oxygen atoms. These primary building units then join to form a porous 3-dimensional framework. Zeolites are commonly used as molecular sieves, adsorbents, ion-exchangers, or catalysts. In catalysis, zeolites are advantageous because they possess high acidity and different pore sizes in molecular dimensions [6,7]. The acidity of the zeolites usually plays a critical role in catalyzing different organic reactions. The type and the concentration of acid sites can be controlled by the nature and number of isomorphously substituted trivalent or tetravalent cations such as Al^{3+} , Ga^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Ge^{4+} , Ti^{4+} , and others [8–10]. Three-valent elements provide Brønsted acid sites (accompanied by Lewis sites formed as the consequence of deficiency in zeolite framework), while incorporation of tetra-valent elements affords mainly Lewis acid sites. The size of the micropores in zeolites defines which

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: maksym.opanasenko@natur.cuni.cz (M. Opanasenko).

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molecules can access the acid sites located inside, allowing only diffusion of the molecules with dimensions similar to or smaller than the pore opening. In addition, a high selectivity to a particular product can be achieved if the pore opening and the product molecule are of similar size [11]. Thymol synthesis from *m*-cresol alkylation over several aluminosilicate zeolites has been studied in the literature [12–15]. However, we still do not know how the type and strength of acid sites and how the pore sizes in zeolites systematically affect the catalytic outcome in terms of *m*-cresol conversion and thymol yield, so that it can guide us into the controlled design of optimal catalysts for this reaction. These effects can be studied with a set of model catalysts synthesized from a germanosilicate zeolite as the starting material.

Due to the bigger size of the Ge atom than the Si, the Ge–O–Si bond in germanosilicates can bear a lower angle limit compared to Si–O–Si, bringing flexibility to the framework through its relaxation [16]. As a result, small building units, e.g. double-4-rings, are characteristic for Ge-containing zeolites. In UTL, these germanium-rich double-4-rings are the units connecting dense silica layers. Due to the structure-directing features of Ge and the chemical flexibility of Ge–O bonds, UTL zeolite can be tailored in two ways. The first way is the incorporation of a heteroelement (Al, Ga, Fe, B, or In) into the framework via isomorphous substitution, which can be done using direct [17] or post-synthesis [18, 19] methods. The second way is changing the interlayer connections via ADOR (Assembly-Disassembly-Organization-Reassembly). On the one hand, isomorphous substitution with different heteroelements provides a set of UTL zeolites (Al-, Ga-, Fe-, B-, and In-UTL) [20] with different acidities and the same pore sizes. On the other hand, ADOR gives a set of isorecticular zeolites (Al-UTL, Al-IPC-7, and Al-IPC-2) with the same heteroelement and the same structure of zeolitic layers but different pore sizes [7,21,22].

In this study, we investigate the key role of acidity (type and strength) and the key role of pore size of the zeolite on thymol synthesis from *m*-cresol to understand the effect of each parameter. For this purpose, we compare the catalytic behavior of Al-, Ga-, Fe-, B-, and In-UTL to shed light on the effect of the acidity, and we compare the catalytic performance of Al-UTL, Al-IPC-7, and Al-IPC-2 to give us insight into the effect of the pore size. The catalytic data of the two sets of UTL-based catalysts are finally compared with those of commercial microporous zeolite Al-FAU (USY), microporous Al-MFI (ZSM-5), and mesoporous molecular sieve Al-MCM-41 as reference materials.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Synthesis (materials)

2.1.1. Synthesis of SDA

The structure directing agent (SDA) 2-ethyl-6-azoniaspiro- [5, 5]-undecane hydroxide was synthesized similar to the method described in Ref. [23], and it was used for the synthesis of Al-UTL, Ga-UTL, Fe-UTL, B-UTL, and In-UTL. To prepare the SDA, 33.76 g of 1,5-dibromopentane (97 %, Sigma Aldrich) was mixed with 116.33 g acetonitrile (≥ 99 %, Sigma Aldrich) in a 500 ml round-bottom flask. Then, 24.37 g of K_2CO_3 (≥ 99.0 % dry basis, Lach-ner, Czech Republic) was added to this solution. Afterwards, 19 ml of 2-ethylpiperidine (> 98 %, TCI Chemicals) was added dropwise under stirring. The mixture was then heated to 85 °C and was refluxed overnight. Acetonitrile was evaporated from the mixture, the product was dissolved in ethanol, and the insoluble compounds were filtered. After evaporating the ethanol, cold diethyl ether was added to this mixture to precipitate the product. The solid product was crushed and left under the hood overnight and it was vacuum-dried afterwards. The synthesized Br-form of the SDA was ion-exchanged with the Ambersep 900 (OH) resin (2 eq. relative to the SDA) to get the hydroxide form of the SDA.

2.1.2. Synthesis of Al-UTL, Ga-UTL, Fe-UTL, B-UTL, and In-UTL

Al-UTL, Ga-UTL, Fe-UTL, B-UTL, and In-UTL zeolites were

synthesized using respective metal hydroxides (or boric acid in case of B-UTL) following ref. [22]. $Ga(OH)_3$ was prepared by precipitation from the reaction of hydrated $Ga(NO_3)_3$ (99.9 %, Sigma Aldrich) with an aqueous solution of NH_3 (28 %, VWR), $Fe(OH)_3$ was prepared by precipitation from the reaction of hydrated $Fe(NO_3)_3$ (≥ 99.95 %, Sigma Aldrich) with the NH_3 solution, and $In(OH)_3$ was prepared by precipitation using reaction of hydrated $In(NO_3)_3$ (99.99 %, Sigma Aldrich) with ammonia. To prepare the synthesis gel mixture, 2.35 g of GeO_2 (≥ 99.99 %, Sigma Aldrich) was dissolved in 30 ml of 0.6 M solution of the SDA. An appropriate amount of either $Al(OH)_3$ (≥ 98 %, Acros Organics), $Ga(OH)_3$, $Fe(OH)_3$, boric acid (≥ 99.5 %, VWR), or $In(OH)_3$ was added to the solution to have Si/M (M = Al, Ga, Fe, B, or In) ratio of 66. When fully dissolved, 2.66 g of fumed silica was added gradually, and the mixture was stirred for 1 h at room temperature. Then, the pH of the mixture was adjusted to 10 or 11 (depending on the heteroelement) by adding concentrated HCl solution (37 %, VWR). The prepared gel was transferred into a Teflon-lined autoclave and was placed in the oven. The crystallization occurred at 175 °C under rotation for 21 days in the case of Al-UTL, 8 days for Ga-UTL, and 7 days for Fe-, B-, and In-UTL. The solids were filtered, washed with deionized water (3 times), dried at 60 °C (12 h) and calcined at 550 °C (temperature ramp 1 °C/min) for 6 h under airflow.

2.1.3. Synthesis of Al-IPC-7 and Al-IPC-2

Al-IPC-7 and Al-IPC-2 zeolites were synthesized according to Ref. [21]. Al-IPC-7 zeolite was synthesized by the treatment of the calcined Al-UTL with 3 M aqueous solution of $Al(NO_3)_3$ (liquid/solid w/w = 100) for 16 h at 60 °C. Subsequently, the solid was separated by centrifugation and washed with 0.01 M HCl and deionized water. The solid was dried at 60 °C overnight. The synthesized Al-IPC-7 zeolite was calcined at 550 °C (1 °C/min) for 6 h.

Al-IPC-2 zeolite was prepared by the treatment of calcined Al-UTL with 1 M aqueous solution of $Al(NO_3)_3$ (liquid/solid w/w = 100) for 16 h at room temperature. The solid was filtered, washed with 0.01 M HCl and deionized water, and dried at 60 °C overnight. The synthesized Al-IPC-2 zeolite was calcined at 550 °C (1 °C/min) for 6 h.

2.1.4. Synthesis of Al-MCM-41

Al-MCM-41 was synthesized according to Ref. [24]. First, 0.33 g aluminum sulfate hexadecahydrate (> 99 %, Lach-ner, Czech Republic) was added to a solution of 10.60 g sodium metasilicate nonahydrate (44–47.5 % total solids, Thermo Scientific) in 25 ml deionized water under 800 rpm stirring at room temperature. Then, the pH of the solution was set to 10.5 by adding 33 ml of 1 M H_2SO_4 (95 %, Acros Organics) under stirring to form a gel. Subsequently, an aqueous solution of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) was prepared separately by dissolving 6.78 g of CTAB (≥ 99 %, VWR) in 16 ml deionized water. The CTAB solution was gradually added to the previous solution containing the Si and Al sources. The resulting mixture was stirred for 1 h at room temperature, transferred into an autoclave, and placed into the oven. Crystallization occurred at 170 °C for 14 h under static conditions. The solid was filtered, washed with deionized water, and dried at 60 °C overnight. The synthesized mesoporous molecular sieve Al-MCM-41 was calcined at 550 °C (1 °C/min) for 6 h under airflow.

2.1.5. Commercial Al-FAU and Al-MFI

Hydrogen form of the USY zeolite (CBV 780) with Si/Al ratio of 40 and ammonium form of ZSM-5 zeolite (CBV 3024E) with Si/Al ratio of 15 were purchased from Zeolyst International, and they are denoted here by Al-FAU and Al-MFI, respectively.

2.2. Characterization

To investigate the phase purity and the crystallinity of the catalysts, powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) analysis was performed on a D8 ADVANCE BRUKER diffractometer equipped with a LYNXEYE XE-T

detector in the Bragg–Brentano geometry using Cu K α ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) radiation. Data were collected in 2θ range of $3\text{--}40^\circ$ (or $1\text{--}40^\circ$ for Al-MCM-41) with 0.021° step size and 0.8 s time per step (or 0.020° step size and 1.7 s time per step for Al-MCM-41). To investigate the morphology of the catalysts, SEM images of the samples were taken using a JEOL JSM-6380 LV Scanning Electron Microscope. The SEM images were collected on a $1 \mu\text{m}$ scale, and were used as complementary information to PXRD analysis.

To investigate the type, concentration, and the strength of acid sites, Fourier Transformed Infra-Red (FTIR) analysis of pyridine probe molecule adsorbed on the catalysts was performed using a NICOLET iS50 FT-IR molecular spectrometer equipped with a deuterated triglycine sulfate (DTGS) detector. Prior to the measurement, the samples were pressed to form self-supporting wafers with density of 10 mg/cm^2 , followed by activation under vacuum at 450°C for 4 h. Pyridine adsorption (partial pressure 3.5 Torr) was performed for 20 min at 150°C . Desorption of adsorbed pyridine was performed for 20 min at 150 , 250 , and 350°C , and the related spectra were collected (systematic error 0.1 cm^{-1}). To calculate the concentration of the Brønsted and Lewis acid sites, molar absorption coefficients were taken from the literature [25].

To obtain the bulk chemical composition of the catalysts, Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectroscopy (ICP-MS) was performed on an Agilent 7900 ICP-MS. 50 mg of each sample was digested in 1.8 ml of HNO_3 (67–69 %, ANALPURE), 5.4 ml of HCl (34–37 %, ANALPURE), and 1.8 ml of HF (47–51 %, ANALPURE), and it was then transferred into a closed Teflon vessel, placed in a Speedwave XPERT Berghof microwave, and heated at 210°C ($5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$) for 25 min. After cooling down, the complexation of the surplus HF was done by adding 12 ml of H_3BO_3 ($\geq 99.5\%$, VWR) and further treatment in the microwave at 190°C ($5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$) for 10 min. Finally, the obtained cooled solutions were diluted for analysis.

To investigate the textural properties of the catalysts, N_2 adsorption-desorption analysis was carried out on a Micromeritics 3Flex Surface Characterization Analyzer at -196°C . Before the measurements, the samples were degassed on a Micromeritics Smart Vac Prep instrument under vacuum, starting at an ambient temperature up to 110°C ($1^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$) until the residual pressure of 13.3 Pa was achieved. After heating at 110°C for 1 h, the temperature was increased to 250°C ($1^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$) and maintained for 8 h. The BET area was evaluated using Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method. The adsorbed amount at relative pressure $P/P_0 = 0.95$ reflects the total adsorption capacity (V_{tot}). The t-plot method was used to evaluate the volume of micropores (V_{mic}) of the zeolites. The mesopore size distribution was calculated by DFT method (N_2 @ -196°C , cylindrical pores in an oxide surface).

2.3. Catalysis

Liquid phase FC alkylation of m-cresol with 2-propanol was performed in a 25 ml BÜCHI AG stainless steel autoclave equipped with a magnetic stirrer, a heating jacket and a sampling probe. The catalysts were activated at 450°C for 6 h prior to the reaction. The catalytic reaction occurred at 200°C , with $m_{\text{catalyst(g)}}:n_{\text{m-cresol(mol)}}:n_{\text{2-propanol(mol)}}$ equal to $0.2:0.1:0.02$. Sulfolane was used as the internal standard for gas chromatography (GC) analysis. The samples were taken hourly during 4 h contact time. Each sample was diluted ($\times 10$) by toluene before GC analysis. An Agilent 8860 GC system with a low polarity HP-5 column ($30 \text{ m} \times 320 \mu\text{m} \times 0.25 \mu\text{m}$) connected to a flame ionization detector (FID) was used to analyze the reaction mixture. Nitrogen was used as the carrier gas in the GC system.

Thymol ($\geq 98\%$, Alfa Aesar), 4-isopropyl-3-methylphenol (99 %, Sigma Aldrich), and isopropyl-3-methylphenyl ether (90.2 %, Apollo Scientific) standards were used for compound identification and calibration. A GC-MS system consisting of Thermo Scientific TRACE 1310 GC with a TG-5MS column and ISQ LT Single Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer (MS) was used to identify the other products. Conversion of m-cresol (X), selectivity to each product (S), and the yield of each product

(Y) were calculated from Eqs. (1)–(3), respectively.

$$X = [(n(\text{reactant})_0 - n(\text{reactant})_t) / n(\text{reactant})_0] \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

$$S = [n(\text{product})_t / \Sigma n(\text{product})_t] \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

$$Y = [n(\text{product})_t / n(\text{reactant})_0] \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

where $n(\text{reactant})_0$ and $n(\text{reactant})_t$ are the amounts of the reactant in the reaction mixture initially and after a specific time t . $n(\text{product})_t$ is the amount of the product formed after a specific time t , and $\Sigma n(\text{product})_t$ is the sum of the amounts of the products in the reaction mixture at time t .

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization

The PXRD patterns (Fig. 1) of the synthesized samples correspond to those of similar materials in the literature [21]. The position of the first peak (200), related to the d-spacing of the interlayer distance, was almost the same (at $2\theta \approx 6.2^\circ$) in the PXRD pattern of Al-UTL, Ga-UTL, Fe-UTL, B-UTL, and In-UTL. Some of the other characteristic peaks of the UTL topology appeared at $2\theta \approx 7.0^\circ$, 7.4° , 8.3° , 9.6° , 22.7° , and 26.2° . The position of the (200) peaks was shifted toward higher angles of $2\theta \approx 7.6^\circ$ for Al-IPC-7 and $2\theta \approx 7.7^\circ$ for Al-IPC-2, indicating a decrease in the average interlayer d-spacing in the order of $\text{Al-UTL} > \text{Al-IPC-7} > \text{Al-IPC-2}$. This reflects the decrease in the ratio between the fraction of double-4-ring building units and smaller single-4-rings in the same order. The PXRD patterns of Al-FAU and Al-MFI corresponded to the topologies of these reference zeolites [26]. The PXRD pattern of Al-MCM-41 showed an intense peak at $2\theta \approx 2.0^\circ$ corresponding to the reflections from the (100) plane and other characteristic peaks in the range of $2\theta \approx 3\text{--}6^\circ$, which were in agreement with the literature data [24].

Complementary to the PXRD analysis, the SEM images of the samples (Fig. S1) were collected to confirm phase purity and to compare the morphology with the reported materials of the same type [21,22]. Practically same crystals of Al-UTL, Ga-UTL, Fe-UTL, B-UTL, and In-UTL had plate-like rectangular shape with an average size of about $4 \mu\text{m}$ on the longest side. Smaller crystals of Al-IPC-7 and Al-IPC-2 ($\approx 3 \mu\text{m}$) showed similar morphology to that of Al-UTL, but with a tendency to agglomerate. The SEM images of Al-FAU and Al-MFI resembled their analogues in the literature [13], the same as Al-MCM-41 having elongated rod-like morphology, which appeared as aggregates [27].

FTIR spectra in the $1700\text{--}1400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ wavenumber region of the adsorbed pyridine upon desorption of the physisorbed molecules at 150°C for Al-UTL, Ga-UTL, Fe-UTL, B-UTL, and In-UTL (Fig. 2a–e) showed characteristic absorption bands for pyridine molecules adsorbed on the zeolite Lewis (ring vibration mode $\nu(19b)$ around 1455 cm^{-1}) and Brønsted acid sites ($\nu(19b)$ around 1545 cm^{-1}). The characteristic absorption band for pyridine adsorbed on Lewis acid sites appeared at 1454 , 1456 , 1448 , 1454 , and 1452 cm^{-1} for Al-UTL, Ga-UTL, Fe-UTL, B-UTL, and In-UTL, respectively. The characteristic absorption band for pyridine on Brønsted acid sites appeared at 1545 and 1546 cm^{-1} for Al-UTL and Ga-UTL, respectively, and it is hardly detectable for Fe-UTL, B-UTL, and In-UTL. Between these two bands, a strong absorption band appeared around 1490 cm^{-1} ($\nu(19a)$) in all UTL samples for pyridine interaction with both Brønsted and Lewis sites. Another strong band was $\nu(8a)$ at 1621 cm^{-1} for Al-UTL, 1619 cm^{-1} for Ga-UTL, 1608 cm^{-1} for Fe-UTL, 1615 cm^{-1} for B-UTL, and 1614 cm^{-1} for In-UTL, which corresponds to the pyridine interacting with Lewis acid sites. The weak absorption band around 1576 cm^{-1} corresponds to the remaining physisorbed pyridine molecules on the zeolites. A small band around 1596 cm^{-1} was present in all UTL samples along with a slight shoulder around 1445 cm^{-1} (less pronounced for Al-UTL and Ga-UTL), which corresponds to pyridine hydrogen-bonded to silanols that were not acidic enough to protonate the pyridine; i. e. weak Brønsted acid sites.

Fig. 1. PXRD patterns of (a) Al-UTL, (b) Ga-UTL, (c) Fe-UTL, (d) B-UTL, (e) In-UTL, (f) Al-IPC-7, (g) Al-IPC-2, (h) Al-FAU, (i) Al-MFI, and (j) Al-MCM-41.

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra in the 1700–1400 cm^{-1} wavenumber region of adsorbed pyridine upon desorption at 150, 250, and 350 °C for (a) Al-UTL, (b) Ga-UTL, (c) Fe-UTL, (d) B-UTL, (e) In-UTL, (f) Al-IPC-7, (g) Al-IPC-2, (h) Al-FAU, (i) Al-MFI, and (j) Al-MCM-41.

Finally, the band at 1637 cm^{-1} in the spectra of Al-UTL, Ga-UTL, and Fe-UTL also correspond to pyridine on Brønsted acid sites [28]. Thus, the FTIR spectra confirmed that the UTL samples had both Brønsted and Lewis acid sites, with Al-UTL and Ga-UTL expected to have a higher concentration and stronger Brønsted acid sites. The respective FTIR spectra of Al-IPC-7 and Al-IPC-2 isorecticular zeolites (Fig. 2f and g) and those of Al-FAU, Al-MFI, and Al-MCM-41 reference materials (Fig. 2h–j) also showed the characteristic absorption bands for pyridine on Lewis acid sites and pyridine on Brønsted acid sites.

As the desorption temperature was raised from 150 to 250 and 350 °C, only strong acid sites were able to maintain interaction with the adsorbed pyridine molecules, thus the intensity of the respective bands decreased with increasing temperature (Fig. 2, 150, 250, and 350 °C). The concentrations of Brønsted and Lewis acid sites in the UTL samples were calculated from the FTIR integrated absorption band areas after pyridine desorption at 150 °C. Concentrations of acid sites did not correlate with the chemical compositions from ICP-MS analysis (Table 1), but were rather related to the nature of the three-valent

element (Al, Ga, Fe, B, or In) and its affinity to substitute Si in the framework. Fe-UTL had the highest concentration of Lewis acid sites ($C_L = 0.17\text{ mmol/g}$) among the UTL zeolites. The concentration of Brønsted acid sites was higher for Al-UTL ($C_B = 0.03\text{ mmol/g}$) and Ga-UTL ($C_B = 0.02\text{ mmol/g}$) and comparably lower for Fe-UTL ($C_B = 0.01\text{ mmol/g}$), B-UTL ($C_B = 0.01\text{ mmol/g}$), and In-UTL ($C_B = 0.003\text{ mmol/g}$, formally below the detection limit), confirming that Al-UTL and Ga-UTL possessed more Brønsted acid sites among the UTL samples. The respective concentration of Brønsted and Lewis acid sites in Al-IPC-7 and Al-IPC-2 isorecticular zeolites and those of Al-FAU, Al-MFI, and Al-MCM-41 reference materials were calculated in the same way as for the UTL samples (Table 1).

The ratio (%) of Brønsted and Lewis acid sites preserving the interaction with the basic probe molecule even at 350 °C to those at 150 °C was considered as the indication of the strength of each type of acid sites ($C_{350\text{ °C}}/C_{150\text{ °C}}$, Table 1). 33 % of Brønsted acid sites in Al-UTL and 50 % of Brønsted acid sites in Ga-UTL were strong enough to maintain interacting with pyridine at 350 °C. On the contrary, Fe-UTL, B-UTL, and In-

Table 1

Chemical composition, Brønsted, Lewis, and total acid sites concentration and strength of sites in the catalysts (*Chemical composition of B-UTL and In-UTL were calculated from Energy Dispersive X-ray analysis).

Sample	Si/M (ICP-MS)	Pyridine desorption temperature (°C)	C _B (mmol/g)	C _L (mmol/g)	C _{tot} (mmol/g)	(C _{B, 350 °C} /C _{B, 150 °C}) × 100	(C _{L, 350 °C} /C _{L, 150 °C}) × 100
Al-UTL	52	150	0.06	0.10	0.16	33	60
		250	0.04	0.06	0.10		
		350	0.02	0.06	0.08		
Ga-UTL	40	150	0.02	0.13	0.15	50	50
		250	0.01	0.08	0.09		
		350	0.01	0.07	0.08		
Fe-UTL	60	150	0.01	0.17	0.18	0	40
		250	0.01	0.09	0.10		
		350	0	0.06	0.06		
B-UTL	61*	150	0.01	0.09	0.10	0	10
		250	0	0.02	0.02		
		350	0	0.01	0.01		
In-UTL	166*	150	0.003	0.07	0.08	0	10
		250	0	0.02	0.02		
		350	0	0.01	0.01		
Al-IPC-7	13	150	0.12	0.16	0.28	60	70
		250	0.10	0.14	0.24		
		350	0.07	0.11	0.18		
Al-IPC-2	56	150	0.07	0.07	0.14	90	70
		250	0.07	0.05	0.12		
		350	0.06	0.05	0.11		
Al-FAU	43	150	0.07	0.04	0.11	70	50
		250	0.07	0.02	0.09		
		350	0.05	0.02	0.07		
Al-MFI	16	150	0.79	0.08	0.87	70	50
		250	0.68	0.05	0.73		
		350	0.55	0.04	0.59		
Al-MCM-41	23	150	0.02	0.13	0.15	0	70
		250	0.01	0.11	0.12		
		350	0	0.09	0.09		

UTL did not possess any strong enough Brønsted acid sites to keep the interaction with pyridine at 350 °C. Thus, Brønsted acid sites generated as a result of the presence of Al or Ga in the framework were stronger than those generated by Fe and B (In-UTL already had a low concentration of Brønsted acid sites at 150 °C). As for the Lewis acid sites, all the UTL samples had some strong Lewis acid sites to keep interacting with pyridine at 350 °C, and the ratio (%) decreased in the order: Al-UTL (60 %) > Ga-UTL (50 %) > Fe-UTL (40 %) > B-UTL = In-UTL (10 %). The only other sample on the list with very weak Brønsted acid sites was Al-MCM-41 mesoporous molecular sieve with no Brønsted acid sites

interacting with pyridine at 350 °C. Al-MCM-41 was our reference material to double check the effect of acidity for easily-accessible acid sites (explained in more details under 3.2. *Catalysis* section). If we assume that the type and strength of acid sites in zeolites influence the catalytic performance, and that strong Brønsted acid sites would be the main centers for m-cresol conversion and thymol formation, then it is expected that Al-UTL and Ga-UTL outperform Fe-UTL, B-UTL, and In-UTL.

All UTL (B-, Al-, Fe-, Ga-, In-UTL) and UTL-derived (Al-IPC-7 and Al-IPC-2) samples exhibited a type (I) adsorption isotherm, characteristic of microporous materials (Fig. 3), which corresponded to similar materials

Fig. 3. N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms at −196.15 °C of Al-UTL, Ga-UTL, Fe-UTL, B-UTL, In-UTL, Al-IPC-7, Al-IPC-2, Al-FAU, Al-MFI, Al-MCM-41, and DFT pore size distribution for Al-MCM-41 (inset).

reported in the literature [21,22] (small hysteresis for Al-IPC-2 is probably caused by agglomeration of its crystals providing interparticle voids, Fig. S1).

In contrast, the adsorption-desorption isotherm for Al-FAU (H-USY) indicates the presence of mesopores generated during the preparation step of this material. For Al-MFI (H-ZSM-5) the slight hysteresis on sorption isotherm was likely caused by (ad/de)sorption in/from the inter-crystalline voids of agglomerated crystals, similar to the case of Al-IPC-2 (Fig. S1). Al-MCM-41 represented a type (IV) isotherm, typical for this mesoporous molecular sieve, with a mean mesopore diameter of 45 Å (pore size distribution analysis in Fig. 3 inset).

The textural properties of the samples (Table 2) corresponded to the typical values reported in the literature [21,22,29,30]. The decrease in the average interlayer d-spacing in the isorecticular set of zeolites (Al-UTL, Al-IPC-7, and Al-IPC-2), which was evaluated from the PXRD analysis, was reflected with a decrease in the micropore volume. The micropore volume decreased from 0.18 cm³/g for Al-UTL to 0.15 cm³/g for Al-IPC-7 and 0.14 cm³/g for Al-IPC-2. UTL framework has perpendicular channels of 12- and 14-membered rings with 5.5 × 8.5 and 7.1 × 9.5 Å pore openings, respectively. IPC-2 framework (OKO) has perpendicular channels of 10- and 12-membered rings with 4.7 × 6.1 and 5.6 × 7.0 Å pore openings, respectively. IPC-7 is a combination of UTL and OKO topologies with 10-, 12-, and 14-membered ring intersecting pores. If we assume that the pore size in zeolites influences the catalytic performance, and that the large and extra-large pores facilitate m-cresol accessibility to the acid sites and provide the necessary space for thymol formation, then it is expected that the conversion follows the order Al-UTL > Al-IPC-7 > Al-IPC-2.

3.2. Catalysis

m-cresol isopropylation was done using m-cresol/2-propanol molar ratio of 5:1 to minimize overalkylation. Alkylation occurs on the ring (C-alkylation) or on the hydroxyl group (O-alkylation) of m-cresol (Fig. 4). Thymol, the desired product of the reaction, is a result of the first pathway: C-alkylation of m-cresol on the ortho-position to the OH group and para-position to the methyl group. Other C-alkylated products are 4-isopropyl-3-methylphenol (4-iPr-3-MPh), 3-isopropyl-5-methylphenol (3-iPr-5-MPh), 2-isopropyl-3-methylphenol (2-iPr-3-MPh), and the dialkylated products 2,4-diisopropyl-3-methylphenol, 2,6-diisopropyl-3-methylphenol, 2,4-diisopropyl-5-methylphenol, and 2,5-diisopropyl-3-

Table 2
Micropore sizes ([26]) and textural properties (from N₂ adsorption-desorption analysis) of the catalysts.

Catalyst	Micropore Size (Å × Å)			BET Area (m ² /g)	V _{mic.} (cm ³ /g)	V _{tot.} (cm ³ /g)
	10-MR ^a	12-MR	14-MR			
Al-UTL	–	5.5 ×	7.1 ×	512	0.18	0.21
Ga-UTL		8.5	9.5	509	0.22	0.26
Fe-UTL				535	0.19	0.21
B-UTL				364	0.16	0.17
In-UTL				445	0.20	0.21
Al-IPC-7		5.5 ×	7.1 ×	428	0.15	0.20
		8.5	9.5			
	4.7 ×	5.6 ×				
	6.1	7.0				
Al-IPC-2	4.7 ×	5.6 ×	–	380	0.14	0.22
	6.1	7.0				
Al-FAU	–	7.4 ×	–	776	0.23	0.39
		7.4				
Al-MFI	5.1 ×	–	–	453	0.15	0.22
	5.5					
	5.3 ×					
	5.6					
Al-MCM-41	Mesopore Size (Å)			945	0.01	0.89
	45					

^a MR = membered ring.

methylphenol.

The conversion of m-cresol and the yield of thymol remained almost constant after 2 h of reaction time (Fig. S2). Thus, the catalytic performance of the samples were evaluated and compared at 2 h contact time (Fig. 5a). Due to high m-cresol/2-propanol molar ratio, the theoretical limit for m-cresol conversion was 20 %, and since the sum of the yields of 3-iPr-5-MPh and 2-iPr-3-MPh was <0.5 % over all the catalysts at 2 h, these products do not appear on Fig. 5a.

The second pathway is O-alkylation, which gives isopropyl-3-methylphenyl ether (iPr-3-MPh ether). iPr-3-MPh ether is less thermodynamically stable than thymol and 4-iPr-3-MPh [13]. As a result, iPr-3-MPh ether can rearrange [31] to give thymol and 4-iPr-3-MPh when the necessary acidity type and strength and enough pore sizes are provided. To check the rearrangement of iPr-3-MPh ether, one catalytic run was performed over Al-FAU at 200 °C with $m_{\text{catalyst(g)}}:n_{\text{m-cresol(mol)}}:n_{\text{iPr-3-MPh ether(mol)}} = 0.2:0.1:0.003$ (Fig. S3). Accordingly, Fig. 5b shows the time evolution of the yield of iPr-3-MPh ether during 4 h of reaction, where a maximum in the initial stages of the reaction is followed by a drop due to transformation to thymol and 4-iPr-3-MPh over a few of the catalysts.

3.2.1. Effect of acid sites type and strength

For the systematic comparison of the effect of the type and strength of acid sites on the catalytic performance, the results obtained using Al-UTL, Ga-UTL, Fe-UTL, B-UTL, and In-UTL, - differing in the acidity (Table 1) - were compared (Fig. 5a). Higher strength of Brønsted acid sites in Al-UTL and Ga-UTL resulted in the highest m-cresol conversion ($X_{\text{m-cresol}} = 19\%$ and 18% : 95 % and 90 % of the theoretical conversion, respectively). On the other hand, the conversion over Fe-UTL, B-UTL, and In-UTL without strong Brønsted acid sites was comparably low ($X_{\text{m-cresol}} = 2\text{--}3\%$). Despite a higher concentration, the Lewis acid sites in Fe-UTL were not efficient in catalyzing the reaction. Thus, it can be concluded that the reaction mainly occurred on strong Brønsted (and to some extent probably on strong Lewis) acid sites. The higher strength of Brønsted acid sites resulted in higher thymol yields over Al-UTL and Ga-UTL ($Y_{\text{thymol}} = 13\%$ and 11% , respectively), in contrast to thymol yield over weak Brønsted acid catalysts Fe-UTL, B-UTL, and In-UTL ($Y_{\text{thymol}} = 1\text{--}2\%$).

In addition, strong Brønsted acid sites in Al-UTL and Ga-UTL facilitated the rearrangement of iPr-3-MPh ether among the UTL samples, evidenced by the decrease in the yield of this product from 1 % at 1 h to almost zero at 2 h over Al-UTL and Ga-UTL (Fig. 5b). On the contrary, the yield of iPr-3-MPh ether gradually increased from negligible at 1 h to 1–2% at 2 h over Fe-UTL, B-UTL, and In-UTL. Thus, the stronger Brønsted acid sites favored thymol formation directly as well as indirectly (via iPr-3-MPh ether rearrangement). The yield of 4-iPr-3-MPh and the yield of the dialkylated products were comparable over the optimum catalysts Al-UTL and Ga-UTL ($Y_{4\text{-iPr-3-MPh}} = 4\%$ and $Y_{\text{dialkylated}} = 2\text{--}3\%$), while no iPr-3-MPh ether was present in the products pool at 2 h contact time in the case of these zeolites. The ratio of the overall yield of C-alkylated products to O-alkylated iPr-3-MPh ether was 19:0 for Al-UTL, 18:0 for Ga-UTL, 2:1 for Fe-UTL, 1:1 for B-UTL, and 2:1 for In-UTL.

Noticeably, the strong Brønsted acid sites associated with Al did not provide any significant advantage in terms of m-cresol conversion compared to those provided by Ga incorporation. Thus, if the deprotonation energy of acid site is small enough (i.e. sufficiently strong acids like Al- and Ga-associated centers), the reaction output is less affected by the catalyst nature.

3.2.2. Effect of pore size

For the systematic comparison of the effect of the pore size on the catalytic performance, the results obtained using Al-UTL, Al-IPC-7, and Al-IPC-2 – differing in porosity and other textural properties (Table 2) – were compared (Fig. 5a). Pores of Al-UTL, the largest among zeolites in the considered isorecticular set, provided the easiest accessibility and

Fig. 4. Reaction scheme of m-cresol isopropylation.

optimum reaction space evidenced by the highest m-cresol conversion ($X_{m\text{-cresol}} = 19\%$). In comparison, m-cresol conversion decreased by decreasing the pore sizes to Al-IPC-7 ($X_{m\text{-cresol}} = 15\%$) and Al-IPC-2 ($X_{m\text{-cresol}} = 6\%$). As expected, Al-IPC-7 with a combined topology of Al-UTL and Al-IPC-2, showed a catalytic performance inferior to Al-UTL and superior to Al-IPC-2. The bigger porosity provided by extra-large and large pores resulted in higher thymol yield over Al-UTL ($Y_{\text{thymol}} = 13\%$) and Al-IPC-7 ($Y_{\text{thymol}} = 8\%$), in contrast to thymol yield over medium pores and fewer large pores in Al-IPC-2 ($Y_{\text{thymol}} = 2\%$).

In addition, extra-large porosity was necessary for the efficient rearrangement of iPr-3-MPh ether among the isoreticular zeolites, evidenced by the different trends (either a fast decrease, a slow decrease, or a gradual increase) in the yield evolution of this product (Fig. 5b). The yield of iPr-3-MPh ether quickly decreased from 1% at 1 h to almost zero at 2 h over Al-UTL, compared to a slower decrease from 3% at 1 h to 2% at 4 h over Al-IPC-7. On the contrary, the yield of iPr-3-MPh ether gradually increased from 2% at 1 h to almost 4% at 4 h over Al-IPC-2. Thus, the extra-large and large porosity accompanied with strong Brønsted acidity favored thymol formation directly as well as indirectly (via iPr-3-MPh ether rearrangement). The yield of 4-iPr-3-MPh (4% → 3% → 1%) and the yield of the dialkylated products (2% → 1% → 0%) decreased with a decrease in pore size and micropore volume in the order Al-UTL > Al-IPC-7 > Al-IPC-2. No iPr-3-MPh ether was present in

the products pool at 2 h contact time in case of Al-UTL. The ratio of the overall yield of C-alkylated products to O-alkylated iPr-3-MPh ether was 19:0 for Al-UTL, 12:3 for Al-IPC-7, and 3:3 for Al-IPC-2.

3.2.3. Comparison with reference materials

Both the acidity and the porosity properties of the catalyst were important for maximizing thymol yield. Al-MCM-41, a mesoporous molecular sieve, with excellent accessibility of acid sites (Table 2), did not possess strong Brønsted acid sites (Table 1). As a result, it exhibited a poor catalytic performance ($X_{m\text{-cresol}} = 5\%$ and $Y_{\text{thymol}} = 2\%$), comparable to those of Fe-, B-, and In-UTL ($X_{m\text{-cresol}} = 2\text{--}3\%$ and $Y_{\text{thymol}} = 1\text{--}2\%$) with weak but accessible Brønsted acid sites. The results confirmed that not only the acid sites must be accessible by m-cresol, but also they must possess strong Brønsted acidity for a high conversion and thymol yield.

The catalytic performance of Al-UTL ($X_{m\text{-cresol}} = 19\%$ and $Y_{\text{thymol}} = 13\%$) was comparable to that of Al-FAU ($X_{m\text{-cresol}} = 20\%$ and $Y_{\text{thymol}} = 14\%$), while the results from Al-IPC-2 ($X_{m\text{-cresol}} = 6\%$ and $Y_{\text{thymol}} = 2\%$) was comparable to that of Al-MFI ($X_{m\text{-cresol}} = 8\%$ and $Y_{\text{thymol}} = 3\%$). However, the catalytic performance of Al-IPC-7 ($X_{m\text{-cresol}} = 15\%$ and $Y_{\text{thymol}} = 8\%$) was in between these two extremes (Fig. 5a). The order of the catalytic performance Al-UTL (\approx Al-FAU) > Al-IPC-7 > Al-IPC-2 (\approx Al-MFI) confirmed that pores of at least 12-MR could provide easier

Fig. 5. (a) Yield of products and m-cresol conversion (black squares) at 2 h and (b) yield of iPr-3-MPh ether over reaction time; temperature = 200 °C, $m_{\text{catalyst(g)}}:m_{\text{m-cresol(mol)}}:m_{\text{2-propanol(mol)}} = 0.2:0.1:0.02$.

accessibility of m-cresol to the acid sites and the necessary reaction space to form thymol. The more large and extra-large pores were there in the zeolitic framework, the higher were the conversion and thymol yield. In other words, strong Brønsted acid sites in Al-IPC-2 and Al-MFI (Table 1) were not accessible for m-cresol due to pore size restrictions; hence both zeolites showed poor catalytic performance.

3.2.4. Selectivity to thymol

The selectivity of the optimum catalysts (Al-UTL, Ga-UTL, and Al-FAU) to thymol were compared at an average of 13 % m-cresol conversion, and the selectivity of the non-optimum catalysts (Al-IPC-7, Al-IPC-2, and Al-MFI) to thymol were compared at an average of 8 % conversion, which was the maximum conversion that Al-IPC-2 and Al-MFI could reach (Fig. 6). However, Fe-, B-, and In-UTL, and Al-MCM-41 were excluded from the selectivity comparisons because their weak Brønsted acid sites were unable to provide meaningful m-cresol

conversion.

Al-UTL and Ga-UTL had a high selectivity to thymol ($S_{\text{thymol}} = 54\%$ and 53% , respectively) because of the strong Brønsted acidity brought by Al and Ga, and the optimum space brought by large and extra-large pores in their framework. Comparably, Al-FAU had 54% selectivity to thymol, because it also had strong Brønsted acid sites accessible via 12-MR pores, and a large cavity, which provided additional reaction space. Although iPr-3-MPh ether was formed at lower contact times over the optimum zeolites ($S_{\text{iPr-3-MPh ether}} = 29\%$ over Al-UTL, 20% over Ga-UTL, and 24% over Al-FAU), these zeolites were able to catalyze the rearrangement of this product to thymol and 4-iPr-3-MPh over time.

In contrast, Al-IPC-2 and Al-MFI were the most selective to iPr-3-MPh ether ($S_{\text{iPr-3-MPh ether}} = 52\%$ and 50% , respectively), and Al-IPC-7 did not provide a significant difference between the selectivity to thymol and the selectivity to iPr-3-MPh ether ($S_{\text{thymol}} = 42\%$ and $S_{\text{iPr-3-MPh ether}} = 41\%$). These zeolites were not efficient in catalyzing the rearrangement of iPr-3-MPh ether either.

To summarize, Al-UTL, Ga-UTL, and Al-FAU zeolites with strong Brønsted acid sites that could be reached by m-cresol via large and extra-large pore openings not only resulted in higher m-cresol conversion, but they also shifted the distribution in favor of the C-alkylated products.

Fig. 6. Selectivity of catalysts to thymol and other products at an average of 13 % m-cresol conversion for optimum catalysts (Al-UTL, Ga-UTL, Al-FAU) and an average of 8 % m-cresol conversion for non-optimum catalysts (Al-IPC-7, Al-IPC-2, Al-MFI), reached at various reaction times; temperature = 200 °C and $m_{\text{catalyst(g)}}:m_{\text{m-cresol(mol)}}:m_{\text{2-propanol(mol)}} = 0.2:0.1:0.02$.

4. Conclusions

We used the structurally flexible UTL zeolite and established the effect of acidity and porosity on the catalytic outcome of thymol synthesis via m-cresol isopropylation. The comparison of the catalytic results from isomorphously-substituted Al-UTL, Ga-UTL, Fe-UTL, B-UTL, and In-UTL made it clear that the strong Brønsted acid sites outperform Lewis acid sites in catalyzing m-cresol isopropylation reaction. Additionally, the comparison among the isorecticular zeolites Al-UTL, Al-IPC-7, Al-IPC-2 revealed that large and extra-large pores facilitate the accessibility to the acid sites.

The structure-performance relationship of these catalysts confirmed that the stronger Brønsted acid site in Al-UTL and Ga-UTL led to higher m-cresol conversion and thymol yield ($X_{\text{m-cresol}} = 18\text{--}19\%$ and $Y_{\text{thymol}} = 11\text{--}13\%$), while Fe-, B-, and In-UTL remained far from being efficient catalysts ($X_{\text{m-cresol}} = 2\text{--}3\%$ and $Y_{\text{thymol}} = 1\text{--}2\%$). Furthermore, the bigger pore sizes in Al-UTL led to the best performance ($X_{\text{m-cresol}} = 19\%$ and $Y_{\text{thymol}} = 13\%$), while the performance declined over Al-IPC-7 ($X_{\text{m-cresol}} = 15\%$ and $Y_{\text{thymol}} = 8\%$) and especially over Al-IPC-2 ($X_{\text{m-cresol}} =$

6 % and $Y_{\text{thymol}} = 2\%$) with pore size restrictions.

Different trends in the yield evolution of the O-alkylated product iPr-3-MPh ether were observed, which were directly related to the acidity and porosity properties of the catalysts. Strong Brønsted acid sites and extra-large and large pores allow rearrangement of iPr-3-MPh ether to thymol and 4-iPr-3-MPh over time, boosting thymol yield over Al-UTL, Ga-UTL, and Al-FAU. Synthesized Al-UTL and Ga-UTL zeolites showed as high a selectivity to thymol as micro-mesoporous Al-FAU ($S_{\text{thymol}} = 54\%$), while Al-IPC-7 and Al-IPC-2 were not selective to thymol.

Al-UTL and Ga-UTL - with accessible and strong Brønsted acid sites - showed the best catalytic performance among all synthesized materials tested in this reaction, and they revealed the optimum properties of a zeolite catalyst for thymol synthesis by m-cresol alkylation.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Fateme Poorsharbaaf Ghavi: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Petr Golis:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Martin Kubů:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jan Přeč:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology. **Maksym Opanasenko:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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